

Machine Learning based Temperature-dependent ENDF Evaluation of Beryllium Thermal Scattering Law

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ABSTRACT

Beryllium metal plays a critical role in nuclear systems due to its low neutron absorption, light mass, and efficient scattering behavior. The current ENDF/B-VIII.1 thermal scattering law (TSL) evaluation for beryllium is based on *ab initio* lattice dynamics (AILD) using a temperature-independent (0 K) phonon density of states (DOS) and rigid crystal structure, limiting its physical accuracy at elevated or cryogenic temperatures. This work presents a full temperature-dependent TSL for beryllium metal with temperature effects included for all components of the evaluation. A machine learning molecular dynamics (MLMD) framework was developed to generate temperature-dependent phonon DOS using an all-temperature Spectral Neighbor Analysis Potential trained on *ab initio* data from 20–1200 K. The temperature-dependent crystal lattice was incorporated through experimentally measured thermal expansion of the HCP structure. The resulting phonon DOS and lattice parameters were implemented within the Full Law Analysis Scattering System Hub (FLASSH) system to produce the first fully temperature-dependent File 7 data for beryllium.

Keywords: Thermal Neutron Scattering, Beryllium Metal

1. INTRODUCTION

Beryllium metal is a material of continued interest in nuclear engineering applications due to a unique combination of desirable characteristics, namely, its low neutron absorption probability, small atomic number, and effective neutron scattering [1]. The degradation of beryllium metal in high neutron fluence environments is well characterized as a result of extensive operating history at facilities like the Advanced Test Reactor at Idaho National Laboratory. New projects employing beryllium metal, such as the Microreactor Applications Research Validation and Evaluation (MARVEL) project [2], renew interest in nuclear data evaluations of beryllium.

The scattering of thermal neutrons, defined by their wavelength relative to the target material's interatomic spacing, is dominated by the target's atomic structure and atomic binding. The thermal scattering laws (TSL) capture the effects of the lattice vibrations (phonons) on the neutron spectrum. The modern thermal neutron scattering evaluation of beryllium metal in the ENDF/B-VIII.1 release [3] is based on a phonon density of states (DOS) calculated using *ab initio* lattice dynamics (AILD) [4]. Within the AILD framework, the phonon DOS is calculated using Hellmann-Feynman forces produced by density functional theory (DFT). While AILD offers quantum-level fidelity for the phonon DOS, it is not able to capture temperature effects. As a result of this limitation, the modern thermal scattering evaluation of beryllium metal uses the same temperature-independent (0 K) phonon DOS to determine the number of occupied states for all temperatures. In addition, the evaluation uses a rigid crystal structure for all temperatures.

In this work, a fully temperature-dependent evaluation of the beryllium metal thermal scattering law is developed. A machine learning molecular dynamics (MLMD) framework is applied to calculate the

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temperature-dependent phonon DOS. An all-temperature machine learning potential (MLP) is trained for all ENDF evaluation temperatures. Thermal expansion of the crystal lattice is adopted based on experimental measurements. The thermal neutron inelastic scattering cross section, and the total cross section, are evaluated and compared to the current ENDF release.

2. METHODS

2.1. Machine Learning Molecular Dynamics

Traditional molecular dynamics (MD) simulations based on empirical interatomic potentials allow the efficient simulation of large supercells of particles under various ensembles and transient conditions. The phonon DOS can be calculated from a MD simulation based on the Fourier transform of the velocity autocorrelation function (VACF). The fidelity of classical MD simulations depends on the chosen interatomic potential. A novel approach to reach near-quantum fidelity in MD simulations is through use of machine-learning potentials (MLPs) trained on DFT-based calculations [5].

2.2. Training Scheme for All-Temperature Machine Learning Potential

The development of an all-temperature machine-learning potential for beryllium metal based on AILD simulations followed an iterative approach [6], as illustrated in Figure 1. Initially, single-temperature MLPs were trained, starting with a low temperature, then progressively increasing. The initial training set for the 20 K MLP consisted of a $4 \times 4 \times 2$ supercell containing 128 Be atoms, generated by performing an AILD geometry optimization on the experimental structure. The calculations were performed with MedeA VASP using the ab initio total-energy and molecular-dynamics package VASP (Vienna ab initio simulation package) developed at the Institut für Materialphysik of the Universität Wien [7, 8]. Diversity was introduced into the training set by performing lattice cell scaling (0.95–1.05), and introducing atomic displacement [6]. The training of the initial MLP was performed with MedeA MLPG, using a Spectral Neighbor Analysis Potential (SNAP) as generated by the FitSNAP code [9, 10, 11]. Using the initially trained SNAP potential, a short LAMMPS MLMD calculation under canonical (NVT) ensemble with a Nose-Hoover thermostat was performed with MedeA LAMMPS [12].

Figure 1. Machine learning potential training flowchart for an all-temperature potential

Five configurations were saved at equal time intervals, and a subsequent AILD geometry optimization was performed on each. The final configurations were appended to the training set for the next training iteration. Subsequent training iterations used the isothermal-isobaric (NPT) ensemble during MLMD calculations, for durations of 0.1 ps, 1 ps, and 10 ps. Subsequently, single-temperature SNAP potentials were processed for 293.6 K, 600 K, 1000 K, and 1200 K. A combined training set, comprising the full single temperature training sets for 20-1200 K, was used to train an all-temperature SNAP potential. Figure 2 demonstrates the fitting performance of the all-temperature trained SNAP potential to energies, forces, and stresses of all *ab initio* configurations. The all-temperature trained SNAP potential was then used in MLMD simulations to obtain a sufficient VACF for phonon DOS processing.

Figure 2. Fit performance of SNAP machine learning potential trained on all temperature configurations

2.2.1. Validation of MLMD-based Phonon calculation

A validation of the new approach was performed by calculating a phonon DOS based on the all-temperature trained SNAP potential MLMD at 20 K, and comparing against neutron observables. Figure 3 shows the 20 K phonon DOS based on the all-temperature trained SNAP potential against the AILD based ENDF phonon DOS. The energy locations of major peaks and valleys align well between the ENDF DOS and the temperature-dependent DOS. Excellent alignment is also observed for the low energy acoustic region. The thermal scattering law captures the effect of phonons on the neutron spectrum in the form of the thermal neutron inelastic cross section. The 20 K DOS was substituted for the ENDF DOS to evaluate the perturbation to the inelastic cross section, shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3. 20 K phonon DOS calculated using the all-temperature SNAP potential against the ENDF B-VIII.1 (0 K) phonon DOS

Figure 4. Thermal neutron inelastic scattering cross section at 296 K calculated using the all-temperature SNAP potential-based phonon DOS against the ENDF B-VIII.1 cross section

The maximum difference in the inelastic cross section remains below 5% across the entire thermal energy range. This indicates good agreement in the effects to the thermal neutron energy spectrum, serving as a validation of the all-temperature trained SNAP potential and the MLMD methodology.

2.3. Calculation of Phonon DOS for ENDF Temperatures

The all-temperature trained SNAP potential, described in Section 2.2, was used to calculate the temperature-dependent phonon DOS at all ENDF B-VIII.1 temperatures. A subset of the calculated phonon DOS are shown in Figure 5, alongside the ENDF B-VIII.1 phonon DOS. Two distinct effects emerge with increasing temperature. First, the peaks shift to lower energies. Second, the peaks broaden and soften.

2.4. Temperature Effects on Beryllium Crystal

The second component of the temperature-dependent evaluation of the beryllium thermal scattering law is the inclusion of thermal expansion of the crystal lattice. Beryllium metal crystallizes in two phases, an α - and β -phase. For the temperatures and pressures of interest to nuclear engineering applications, we are concerned with the α -phase, which has a hexagonal close-packed (HCP) crystalline lattice, space group $P6_3/mmc$. The thermal expansion of α -phase beryllium has been tabulated using x-ray diffraction techniques for various temperatures by Meyerhoff et al., Gordon, and Martin et al. [13, 14, 15]. The collection of measured data encapsulates the temperature range used for the ENDF evaluations, as shown in Figure 6. Regression was performed using a fourth-order polynomial functional form to both independent lattice parameters. For the a parameter, the root mean squared error (RMSE) for the fit was 0.002 \AA , with an R^2 of 0.9998. For the c parameter, the RMSE for the fit was 0.006 \AA , with an R^2 of 0.9993. The empirical lattice constants of beryllium metal were tabulated for the ENDF evaluation temperatures in Table I.

2.5. Thermal Neutron Scattering Cross Section Evaluation

The Full Law Analysis Scattering System Hub (FLASSH) was used to evaluate the thermal neutron scattering cross section [16]. The base files used for the evaluation were the existing ENDF/B-VIII.1

Figure 5. Temperature-dependent phonon DOS for Beryllium metal calculated at ENDF B-VIII.1 temperatures using the all-temperature trained SNAP MLP

Table I. Beryllium crystal lattice parameters at ENDF B-VIII.1 temperatures

T (K)	a (Å)	c (Å)	c/a Ratio
77	2.284316	3.580819	1.567567
100	2.284348	3.580779	1.567528
296	2.286879	3.583905	1.567160
400	2.289585	3.587519	1.566886
500	2.292875	3.591886	1.566543
600	2.296706	3.596900	1.566112
700	2.300966	3.602383	1.565596
800	2.305554	3.608207	1.565007
1000	2.315393	3.620593	1.563706
1200	2.325736	3.633970	1.562504

Figure 6. Thermal expansion of Beryllium metal lattice parameters based on experimental measurements [13, 14, 15]

evaluation FLASSH input files. Beryllium data used during the evaluation is shown in Table II. The temperature-dependent SNAP MLMD-based phonon DOS and DOS energy grid calculated from Section 2.3 was substituted in for the AILD-based ENDF/B-VIII.1. The temperature-dependent lattice parameters from Section 2.4 were substituted for the rigid crystal. These substitutions have been used to generate the first fully temperature-dependent File 7 data for beryllium metal. The new data will include temperature-dependent TSL data (MT4) and coherent elastic data (MT2). For each temperature, a separate File 7 file is processed due to the limitation of the ENDF File 7 format to accept only a single set of coherent elastic data (MT2).

Table II. Isotopic composition, atomic mass, and free atom cross section for natural beryllium.

Isotopic composition	Isotope	Atomic mass (u)	Free atom cross section (b)
Natural	^9Be : 100.0%	9.012199	6.153875

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The total cross section of beryllium was calculated using the temperature-dependent total neutron scattering cross section processed with *FLASSH*. At 300 K, the new model yields reasonable agreement with experiment in the sub-Bragg energy region, but both models have a steeper slope than experiment. In this case, deviations from experiment due to coherent inelastic effects are noted for both models. At 600 K and 800 K, the temperature effect is more pronounced, and the new model better captures the magnitude of the cross section below the Bragg edge. Figure 7 shows the new total cross section evaluation for select temperatures on the full range of ENDF temperatures along side the corresponding ENDF/B-VIII.1 total cross section. Figure 8 shows the new thermal neutron inelastic scattering cross section evaluation for select temperatures on the full range of ENDF temperatures along side the corresponding ENDF/B-VIII.1 inelastic cross section. The temperature with the least variation in both the total cross section and thermal neutron inelastic scattering cross section was 296 K, with a maximum inelastic cross section difference of 13%.

Figure 7. Total cross section of Beryllium metal against ENDF B-VIII.1 evaluations and experimental measurements [17, 18, 19]

Figure 8. Thermal neutron inelastic scattering cross section of Beryllium metal against ENDF B-VIII.1 evaluations

The lattice parameters used in the ENDF/B-VIII.1 are experimentally derived at room temperature, thus the only impact to the DOS was the anharmonicity at 296 K. The trend from 296 K to 1200 K is consistent, with a larger observed difference at higher temperatures, peaking with a 23% difference peak at 1200 K. An outlier of this trend was the 77 K cross section, which observed the highest difference. Due to the substantially smaller inelastic cross section below 0.01 eV at 77 K, the cross section is very sensitive to perturbations in the phonon DOS. The impact to the phonon DOS seen at 77 K is overwhelmingly the change in volume as a result of the difference in temperature-dependent lattice parameter.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a temperature-dependent ENDF evaluation of beryllium metal thermal scattering law was developed. An all-temperature machine learning potential was developed using a MLMD framework, enabling the calculation of temperature-dependent phonon density of states across all ENDF evaluation temperatures. Validation of the MLMD methodology at 20 K showed excellent agreement compared to fundamental AILD results for both the phonon DOS and the resulting thermal neutron inelastic scattering cross section, with deviations remaining below 5% over the full thermal energy range.

The temperature-dependent phonon DOS captures two key physical effects: a systematic shift of spectral features toward lower energies, and a broadening of peaks associated with phonon softening. In parallel, experimentally derived thermal expansion data for the HCP beryllium lattice were incorporated to provide temperature-dependent crystal structures for all evaluated temperatures. These combined datasets were implemented within the *FLASSH* TSL and coherent elastic calculations to generate the first fully temperature-dependent File 7 evaluations of beryllium metal.

Comparisons with the ENDF/B-VIII.1 evaluation demonstrated that the new temperature-dependent scattering laws physically meaningful variations at low and high temperatures. At elevated temperatures, the influence of thermal expansion and phonon softening becomes increasingly pronounced, resulting in differences up to 23% in the inelastic cross section at 1200 K.

The methodology presented here establishes a physically consistent pathway for producing temperature-dependent thermal scattering evaluations. Future work will focus on extending the validation of the all-temperature SNAP potential.

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REFERENCES

- [1] T. A. Tomberlin. "Beryllium – A Unique Material in Nuclear Applications." Technical Report INEEL/CON-04-01869, Idaho National Engineering and Environmental Laboratory, Idaho Falls, ID, USA (2004). URL <https://inldigitallibrary.inl.gov/sites/sti/sti/2808485.pdf>.
- [2] D. Gerstner and Y. Arafat. "MARVEL 90% Final Design Report." Program Document INL/RPT-23-74280-Rev000, Idaho National Laboratory, Idaho Falls, ID, USA (2023). URL <https://doi.org/10.2172/2208844>. Issued 01 September 2023.
- [3] G. P. A. Nobre et al. "ENDF/B-VIII.1: Updated Nuclear Reaction Data Library for Science and Applications." (2025). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2511.03564>.
- [4] A. I. Hawari. "Modern Techniques for Inelastic Thermal Neutron Scattering Analysis." *Nuclear Data Sheets*, **volume 118**(1), pp. 172–175 (2014). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0090375214000593>.
- [5] J. L. Wormald, A. J. Trainer, and M. L. Zerkle. "Machine-learned force fields for thermal neutron scattering law evaluations." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 211**, p. 110978 (2025). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306454924006418>.
- [6] J. Gil and A. I. Hawari. "Machine Learning Molecular Dynamics for Thermal Scattering Law Evaluations with Enhanced Temperature Fidelity." In *Proceedings of the 16th Nuclear Data for Science and Technology Conference (ND2025)*. Madrid, Spain (2025). To appear.

- [7] G. Kresse and J. Furthmüller. "Efficient iterative schemes for ab initio total-energy calculations using a plane-wave basis set." *Phys Rev B*, **volume 54**, pp. 11169–11186 (1996). URL <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevB.54.11169>.
- [8] G. Kresse and J. Furthmüller. "Efficiency of ab-initio total energy calculations for metals and semiconductors using a plane-wave basis set." *Computational Materials Science*, **volume 6**(1), pp. 15–50 (1996). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0927025696000080>.
- [9] Materials Design, Inc. *MedeA 3.11.1 (Materials Exploration and Design Analysis)*. 12121 Scripps Summit Drive, Ste 160 San Diego, CA 92131, 3.11.1 edition (2025). URL <https://www.materialsdesign.com>.
- [10] M. A. Wood and A. P. Thompson. "Extending the accuracy of the SNAP interatomic potential form." *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, **volume 148**(24), p. 241721 (2018). URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5017641>.
- [11] M. A. Cusentino, M. A. Wood, et al. "Explicit Multielement Extension of the Spectral Neighbor Analysis Potential for Chemically Complex Systems." *The Journal of Physical Chemistry A*, **volume 124**(26), pp. 5456–5464 (2020). URL <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpca.0c02450>. PMID: 32432859.
- [12] A. P. Thompson, H. M. Aktulga, et al. "LAMMPS - a flexible simulation tool for particle-based materials modeling at the atomic, meso, and continuum scales." *Comp Phys Comm*, **volume 271**, p. 108171 (2022).
- [13] R. W. Meyerhoff and J. F. Smith. "Anisotropic Thermal Expansion of Single Crystals of Thallium, Yttrium, Beryllium, and Zinc at Low Temperatures." *Journal of Applied Physics*, **volume 33**(1), pp. 219–224 (1962). URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1728490>.
- [14] P. Gordon. "A High Temperature Precision X-Ray Camera: Some Measurements of the Thermal Coefficients of Expansion of Beryllium." *Journal of Applied Physics*, **volume 20**(10), pp. 908–917 (1949). URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1698252>.
- [15] A. J. Martin and A. Moore. "The structure of beryllium, with particular reference to temperatures above 1200°C." *Journal of the Less Common Metals*, **volume 1**(2), pp. 85–93 (1959). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0022508859900451>.
- [16] N. C. Fleming, C. A. Manring, B. K. Laramee, J. P. W. Crozier, E. Lee, and A. I. Hawari. "FLASSH 1.0: Thermal Scattering Law Evaluation and Cross-Section Generation for Reactor Physics Applications." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 197**(8), pp. 1887–1901 (2023). URL <https://doi.org/10.1080/00295639.2023.2194195>.
- [17] K. Kanda, H. Kadotani, et al. "Effect of Temperature on Total Cross Section of Beryllium for Thermal Neutrons." *Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology*, **volume 12**(10), pp. 601–605 (1975). URL <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/18811248.1975.9733160>. Data taken from the EXFOR database, file EXFOR 21657 dated 1980, retrieved from the IAEA Nuclear Data Services website.
- [18] G. M. Borgonovi, D. H. Houston, et al. "INTEGRAL NEUTRON THERMALIZATION. Annual Summary Report, October 1, 1968– September 30, 1969." Technical report, Gulf General Atomic, Inc., San Diego, CA (United States) (1969). URL <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/4158293>.
- [19] H. Palevsky and R. R. Smith. "Private communication." (1952). Data taken from the EXFOR database, file EXFOR 11204 dated 1952, retrieved from the IAEA Nuclear Data Services website.